

The Effect of Using Creative Drama on Developing Innovative Thinking and Achievement in Teaching English Language among 6th Grade Students at Lewa Al Jamea Directorate of Education

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 21, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Creative drama, Innovative thinking, Achievement</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4708041</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to identify the effect of using creative drama on developing innovative thinking and achievement in teaching the English language at Lewa Al Jamea Directorate of Education, the sample of the study, which was intentionally chosen, consisted of (120) 6th grade students, The study sample was distributed randomly into two groups: The first group is the experimental group and it consisted of (62) students in (DahiyatAlrasheed Girls Highschool) who were taught English language using creative drama, and the second control group consisted of (58) male and female students at Princess Basma School - Abu Nsair, who were taught the English language course in the usual way. After the completion of the teaching, the innovative thinking and achievement tests were applied after verifying their validity and reliability according to the scientific basis, and appropriate statistical methods were used.</i></p> <p><i>The study found the following results:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>The existence of statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the mean of the performance of the two groups of the study on the innovative thinking post-test (fluency, flexibility, and originality) in favor of the experimental group that studied the English language subject using creative drama.</i> - <i>The presence of statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the averages of the performance of the two groups of the study on achievement posttest in favor of the experimental group that studied the English language subject using creative drama.</i>

Introduction

Language is the greatest phenomenon that distinguishes a person from other living things, as it decodes many mysterious symbols from spoken words and vague signs, and in its communication between individuals is easy, and without it the individual cannot express what is going on inside him or depict what is happening around him.

Language skills include speaking, reading, listening and writing skills. In fact, drama depends in its essence on the four language skills, and thus helps to develop it among the learner. As for speech, It is considered the main tool by which the actor expresses the context of the text or the idea, so the success of the student represented in a good expression depends on his ability to perform appropriate body movements, facial expressions expressing his speech, and on his ability to pronounce words carefully and clearly, while varying the pitch of the voice commensurate With the nature of the representational situation, these skills in their entirety help to develop the speech skill of the learner (Al-Qurashi, 2001).

As the drama has a role in the development of reading, listening and writing, the researcher believes that it also has a role in developing the student's linguistic outcome, and identifying new terms in the Arabic language.

Theater teaching and what it includes in terms of theater situations and events develop the learner's ability to face the problems that he may encounter in the future, and our societies are full of problems that face the individual, especially students, either in the school environment or in the community environment, which naturally contributes to the formation of the ideal personality of the individual, and the ability to Interacting with all the atmospheres, circumstances and difficulties that surround it in the future (Afaneh and al-Louh, 2008).

It is possible for the teacher to increase students' motivation, by enabling them to formulate their goals, by following many activities, making them define their educational goals and formulating them in their own language, and helping them to choose the goals that they can achieve, and thus helps students to identify appropriate strategies that must be followed during the attempt to fulfill it (Petri & Covern, 2004).

The researcher believes that the issues and problems discussed during the dramatic work inside the classroom create in the student a strong personality supported by a critical vision, and the ability to solve difficult problems, and work to prepare him for future life.

The problem of the Study

The English language is the language of the age and technology, and it is spread all over the world. However, students face problems in mastering linguistic skills, writing and developing thinking skills, which led to students' weakness in the English language. There have been increasing demands from specialists and educators to develop English language curricula, develop teaching skills for teachers and train them in modern methods. Educators attributed the reasons for students' weakness in the English language to its teaching methods, as the learner cannot interact with practical life unless he mastered the writing skills, and communicate with others. The researcher noticed, through her work as an English language professor at Princess Alia University College, weakness in reading, writing, and forming language structures among female students, which led to a decline in their thinking skills and their level of achievement, and this indicates that there is a clear weakness of students in the foundation level in schools, and thus there is a need to activate modern methods of teaching students in schools, such as the creative drama method, in order for the student to reach the university level with a good level of mastery of the English language. In light of the review of previous studies, it was revealed that there are no studies related to the use of creative drama in the development of innovative thinking - to the best of the researcher's knowledge - and the existence of studies related to achievement and other variables. Some studies have recommended encouraging primary school teachers to employ creative drama through the educational situation, which has a positive effect. Regarding students' attitudes, it also recommended that the use of drama is effective for developing student achievement and retention, and recommended applying it to other variables such as developing the skill of listening and acquiring concepts and trends.

The current study came to identify the effect of using creative drama on developing innovative thinking in teaching English language among sixth-grade students and their achievement at Lewa Al Jamea Directorate of Education.

The aim of the study and its questions

The current study aimed to identify the effect of using creative drama on developing innovative thinking and achievement in teaching English among sixth-graders at Lewa Al Jamea Directorate of Education in Amman.

To achieve the goal, the current study tried to answer the following two questions:

1. What is the effect of using creative drama in teaching the English language course on the development of innovative thinking among 6th grader students, compared to the usual method?
2. What is the effect of using creative drama in teaching English on 6th grader students' achievement, compared to the usual method?

The Importance of the Study

It is hoped that this study will benefit in the following:

1. A new addition to Arabic studies related to the use of the creative drama method.
2. The benefit of educational specialists from curriculum planners, teachers, and supervisors from the results of the current study in planning, directing, and teaching.
3. Keeping pace with recent studies in the field of English language teaching methods, and activating the use of creative drama during the educational situation.
4. Provide a model for the teacher in the way to apply creative drama, and provide him with practical skills and experience to develop the educational process in the classroom.
5. A reference for future studies and the researchers' benefit from the method, procedures, and tools used in it.

The Study Hypotheses

To answer the two study questions, the following two hypotheses were tested:

- There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the development of innovative thinking among sixth-grade students due to the use of creative drama, compared to the usual method.
- There are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the achievement of sixth-grade students due to the use of creative drama, compared to the usual method.

The Study Limits

The study was determined by the following limits:

- Spatial limits: The study was limited to students at DahiyatAlrasheed Girls Highschool and Princess Basma School - Abu Nsair / Amman / at Lewa Al Jamea Directorate of Education.
- Human Limits: Sixth grade students.
- Time limits: the first semester of the academic year 2019/2020
- The objective limit: the fifth unit of the English language subject.

The Study Limitations

The generalization of the results of this study to the community from which the sample was taken or similar communities is determined by indications of the validity and reliability of their tools.

The Definition of the Study Terms

The study terms were defined as follows:

Creative Drama: It is a teaching method that stimulates the building of a free, imaginative world for students without being bound by a written text, and is based on employing methods of role-playing, improvisation, visualization, and gesture, with the aim of presenting a basic idea about a specific topic and then adopting broad and deep ideas around it through the experiences of the student and presenting the results in a representative manner.

It was defined procedurally: that it is based on the integration of physical and mental activity through various dramatic activities that provide the opportunity for students to imagine and act, through the teaching plan prepared by the researcher according to this method.

Innovative thinking: is the process of awareness of problems and weaknesses, searching for solutions, formulating or modifying hypotheses after testing them, and communicating results to others.

It is defined as procedural: that the score obtained by students in the test of innovative thinking skills (fluency, flexibility, originality), according to the Torrance tests of innovative thinking.

Achievement: "the extent to which students comprehend what they have gained from experience through specific academic courses, it is measured by the degree obtained by students in the achievement test prepared for this purpose.

It was defined procedurally: as the total score obtained by students in the achievement test prepared by the researcher according to Bloom's cognitive levels (remember, understand, apply).

Previous Studies

The researcher reviewed some studies such as:

Abu Mansour (2018) conducted a study entitled "The Effect of Using Creative Drama in the Development of innovative thinking and Achievement in the teaching of Arabic language for Fifth Grade students in the Capital Amman". The study aimed to identify the effect of using creative drama on developing innovative thinking and achievement in teaching Arabic in the capital, Amman, and the sample of the study that was chosen by the intentional method consisted of (60) students from the fifth primary grade. The study sample was distributed randomly into two groups: The first group is the experimental group and it consisted of (31) male and female students in the Al-Durra Al-Sharifa School. Arabic language was taught using creative drama, and the second control group consisted of (29) students in Carthage International School. The Arabic language course was taught in the usual way. After the completion of the teaching, the innovative thinking and achievement tests were applied after ensuring their validity and reliability according to the scientific basis, and appropriate statistical methods were used. The study found the following results:

- The existence of statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \dots 5$) between the averages of the two groups' post-study performance on the innovative thinking test (fluency, flexibility, and originality) in favor of the experimental group that studied Arabic language using creative drama.
- There were statistically significant differences at the level of ($5 \dots \alpha$) between the averages of the performance of the two groups of the post study on the achievement test for the benefit of the experimental group that studied the Arabic language subject using creative drama.

Batu, Ertürk and Kaptan (2009) study aims to examine the educational attainment in 2006 of the educational programs for pre-school students. In terms of science operations skills. The study also aims to determine the size of the science operations skills, which are used in the daily lesson plan samples, in educational institutions throughout the year, and the daily lesson plan samples, from different publishing houses, and to determine the level of awareness of pre-school teachers about the skills of science operations. The sample included children, whose age ranges between (60-72) months, in the city of Ankara, Turkey, and a sample was prepared for the interviews to determine the level of awareness among teachers for the pre-school stage. Among the qualitative research techniques; Descriptive, to formulate interviews template. According to the results of the analysis; the results showed that teachers do not give much space to scientific activities in pre-school education, and that the awareness levels of teachers are significantly low, with regard to the skills of science operations.

Shaheen (2009) study aimed to know the effect of using active learning strategies on achievement, and the development of science processes, among fourth grade students. And the science processes (observation, classification, deduction, imposing hypotheses, and controlling variables), the researcher used the experimental design on a sample of fourth grade primary students, at the educational customs administration in Alexandria, and the number of the study sample was (90) male and female students, and it was divided into two groups: One of them is a control, its number is (45) male and female students, the other is experimental, and its number is (45) male and female. The researcher applied to them the study tools that were prepared by her, namely: an achievement test and a test for science operations.

After applying the study, and collecting data; The correlation coefficient between the scores of the students of the experimental group in the achievement test and the telemetry process test was calculated. The correlation coefficient between the scores of the students of the control group in the achievement test, and the science operations test in the distance, was calculated by using the Pearson equation. Active learning, and after using it on the experimental and control group; There are statistically significant differences in favor of the experimental group, compared to the control group.

Ozdemir and Cakmak (2008) study aimed to examine the effect of educational drama on the potential creativity of teachers in the classroom. As a method for this study; an experimental design was used, based on pre-test and post-test. The research sample consisted of (78) fourth-grade students, (50) females and (28) males, who attended the teacher's elementary education program in the Department of Primary Education, College of Education, Kerkali University, in the fall semester, of the 2006-2007 academic year. The information in this study was collected by Torrance Test of Creative Thinking for formal tests - Model A, and this model was applied to the participants after the drama course, and accordingly; the pre-test and post-test were compared. The study concluded that the results of the creative test performed by the students increased to the extent that it included all dimensions of the creative test (fluency, originality, preparation, resistance to premature closing, and stripping of titles). It was also found that the creative test scores of the participants in the pre-test and post-test did not make a big difference, according to the gender variable. The study recommended that drama should be an essential part of the educational teacher program, and more research should be conducted on this.

Abdulhak (2008) study aims to determine whether the native language courses that depend on employing creative drama activities are more efficient in developing oral communication skills for elementary school students than traditional native language courses, the validity of this model was verified by referring it to seven experts, in order to confirm the reliability, and this tool was applied to the experimental group, the control group, as a pre-test and a post-test alike. In line with the objective of this study; The traditional method was used, where the teacher used the book as a main focus for the control group, while drama activities were used to implement the mother tongue lessons on the experimental group. The analysis of the data showed that there is a fundamental difference in the oral communication skills between the two groups: the experimental group and the control group, as the application of drama activities using the mother tongue proved that it has improved pronunciation skills, compared to the traditional teacher's curriculum, which is based on the book only.

Fernsler (2003) conducted a study aimed at investigating the effect of using dialogue drama in teaching basic concepts of social studies for third-grade students in basic achievement in Britain. The study sample consisted of (30) students from Eastern Tense School, they were divided into two groups, an experimental group, a number (15) and a control group, (15). The study used the experimental method and the results of the post-test showed the superiority of the members of the experimental group that received education using dialogue drama.

Method and procedures

This section deals with the study's methodology, its population, its representative sample, its tools, and the statistical treatment that was used to answer the two study questions, and test its two hypotheses, explain the study's variables, design it and clarify the procedures that the researcher followed in implementing the current study.

The Study Methodology

The researcher adopted the quasi-experimental approach for its suitability for the purposes of the study.

The Population of the Study

The study population consists of 6th grade students in the schools at Lewa Al Jamea Directorate of Education.

The Sample of the Study

Two sections of the 6th grade class in two schools at Lewa Al Jamea Directorate of Education were chosen by intentional method in order to take advantage of the capabilities and activities available in them. The two study groups were distributed randomly so that the first section formed the experimental group and it

reached (62) students, it was taught the fifth unit of the English language book for the first semester of 2018/2019 using creative drama, the second section formed the control group, it consisted of (58) students, and the same unit of English language was taught to them in the usual way. Table No. (1) shows the distribution of the study sample according to the group and the school:

Table 1: Distribution of the study sample individuals by group

Group	Number
Experimental	62
Control	58
Total	120

The Study Tools

To answer the study's questions and test its two hypotheses, the researcher prepared and constructed the innovative thinking test and prepared the achievement test as follows:

First: the innovative thinking test

The researcher used the Torrence test for innovative thinking using verbal forms (A) by referring to the test included in previous studies, and the test of the innovative thinking test (fluency, flexibility and originality) was prepared and constructed in accordance with the academic subject and the age stage specified in the current study.

The Test Validity

The validity of the test was verified before its application, by presenting it to a group of arbitrators with competence and experience in this field, and they were (11) arbitrators to express their observations on the language formulation, the relevance of the test items to the students' level, and their representation of the skills of innovative thinking (fluency, flexibility, and originality) the amendment was made based on the evaluators' observations, and the final test was approved.

The Test Reliability

The internal reliability of the test was calculated by calculating the test's reliability factor (Cronbach Alpha) that was applied to a pilot sample and their number (16) students from outside the study sample, where the parameters of the reliability skills of innovative thinking appeared as follows: Fluency (0.84), flexibility (0.80), originality (0.83), and the coefficient of reliability of innovative thinking for the grand total equals (0.82). This is acceptable for the purpose of the study.

Second: The achievement test

To measure the extent to which the objectives of the fifth unit of the English language subject are achieved for 6th grade students, the researcher prepared an achievement test consisting of (30) items of the multiple-choice type for the first semester, so that the test included the first three levels of Bloom's level (Knowledge, comprehension, application) and the achievement test was prepared by following the following steps:

- Determine the general objective of the fifth unit of the 6th grade English language subject.
- Unit five content analysis.
- Determine the educational outcomes of the fifth unit lesson plans.
- Build a table of specifications in light of the vocabulary of the fifth unit.
- Choose test items in light of educational outcomes.
- Determine the test instructions, and the maximum mark for the test (30), where one mark was

placed for each item of the test.

The Test Validity

To ensure the validity of the test, it was presented in its initial form, as it consisted of (30) items, attached to a table of specifications, and behavioral objectives on the group of arbitrators referred to previously, to express their opinion on the extent to which the test represents the behavioral objectives of the educational material, the relevance of its items to the objectives of the topic, as well as the linguistic wording, and its relevance to the level of students, and in light of the comments of the arbitrators, some of the test items were amended in terms of reformulating the substitutions, and no items was deleted and the test was put in its final form.

The Test Reliability

The reliability of the achievement test was verified by applying it to a pilot sample from outside the study sample, as it consisted of (18) male and female students, and the reliability factor was calculated in two ways:

- Internal consistency method, using the Keyword - Richardson equation (KR-20) to measure the internal consistency of the test items, and it reached (.86).
- The method of test/retest where the test was applied to a pilot sample referred to previously, and after two weeks it was repeated again on the same sample, and the Cronbach Alpha coefficient was calculated and reached (0.88), and these values are sufficient for the purposes of the study, the difficulty and discrimination factors were also calculated for the achievement test.

Teaching plan using Creative Drama

The plan was built according to the teaching objectives of the fifth unit of the English language for the first semester, and various strategies were used within the plan, such as brainstorming, and the Six Hats for being staged adorably, and it was combined with the creative Drama method, the researcher included the study a proposed archeology model, and amended, for the CORT program of thinking for its effectiveness in developing innovative thinking and its suitability for all academic levels, and the teaching plan included the following:

1. Learning outcomes for each lesson.
2. The means and resources that were used within the teaching procedures.
3. Teaching procedures used, and activities used during the teaching process.
4. Working papers related to the lesson, and the program of the kurt to think, and the plan was presented to a group of experienced and specialized referees and their observations were taken and the plan was finalized.
5. Equality was found between the two teachers who taught the experimental and control groups in terms of certificates of academic qualification, years of experience, and training courses.

The Study Variables: The study variables were determined as follows:

- Creative Drama Style
- Innovative thinking
- Achievement

The Study Design

O ₂	O ₁	X	O ₂	O ₁	G ₁
O ₂	O ₁	-	O ₂	O ₁	G ₂

whereas:

- G₁ Experimental group
- G₂ Control group
- O₁ Pre and post measurement in the innovative thinking test of the experimental and control groups
- O₂ Pre and post measurement in the achievement test for the experimental and control groups
- X Teaching using the creative drama method
- - Teaching in the usual way

The Statistical Treatment

- To answer the first and second questions, and to verify the two hypotheses of the study, the arithmetic averages, standard deviations and the "T" test of were used for two independent groups.
- The reliability of the innovative thinking and achievement tests were calculated using two methods: the Kjord Richardson (KR-20) equation for internal consistency, and Test/retest.
- The accompanying mono-analysis of variance (ANCOVA) was used because it achieves parity between the two groups (experimental and control) on the pre-test, so its results do not affect the results of the post-test, so there is no need to create parity between the two groups on the pretest.

The Study Procedures

The study was carried out by relying on a set of procedures as follows:

1. Refer to the theoretical literature and previous studies related to the subject of the study.
2. Viewing the Arabic language curriculum for the 6th grade.
3. Analysis of the unit that was selected from the English language curriculum for the 6th grade.
4. Preparing an innovative thinking test, or an achievement test.
5. The two tests presented innovative thinking and achievement to a group of judges.
6. Calculating the reliability of the two tests for innovative thinking and achievement using the (Coder Richardson equation) and (Cronbach's alpha coefficient).
7. Determining the study personnel, by choosing two schools in the intentional way, and choosing two sections to implement the study.
8. Applying the pre-test (innovative thinking and achievement) to the sample members.

9. Sitting with the teacher who taught the experimental group, to explain what the creative drama is, and explain the teaching plan for her.
10. Teaching the assigned study unit using the experimental group's creative drama and teaching it in the usual way for the control group.
11. Arranging periodic visits for the experimental group to check the course of the teaching plan well.
12. Application of the two-dimensional tests (innovative thinking and achievement) on the sample members.
13. Correct the tests of innovative thinking and achievement.
14. Collecting data and analyzing it statistically by using the statistical packages program SPSS.
15. View study results
16. Discussing results, drawing recommendations, and proposals in light of what has been reached.

Procedures for correcting the innovative thinking test

First: Fluency: It was calculated by the number of correct responses that the student responded to in each activity, where one mark is placed for each correct response.

Second: Flexibility: The number of correct responses that the student responded to in each activity was calculated as follows.

1. The first response is not given a degree of elasticity, because elasticity is shifting in direction.
2. The degree of flexibility is zero if the trend does not change in all responses.
3. In the case of repeating the same shift, the student does not receive an additional score, and a score is given for each shift in direction.

Third: Authenticity: The degree of originality was calculated by unpacking the answers of all students into a special table for responses that includes the frequency of each response and its frequency.

The percentage of frequency for each response was calculated by calculating the total frequency of the response over the total responses to the activity. If the frequency rate was less than (5%), the response is considered original, if the prevalence rate is (5%) or more, the answer is considered common, that is, not original, and the sign is not taken into account (Torrance 1993).

The Results of the Study

This is a presentation of the results of the study aimed at identifying the impact of using creative drama on developing innovative thinking and achievement in teaching English among 6th grade students in the capital Amman, by answering the following two questions:

First: The results related to the first question, which stated:

"What is the effect of using creative drama on developing innovative thinking in teaching English language to 6th grade students, compared to the usual method?"

To answer this question, and to test the hypothesis related to it, the means and standard deviations of the performance of the 6th grade basic students in the English language subject were calculated on the post-test of innovative thinking (fluency, flexibility, and originality), and Table (2) shows that.

Table 2: Means and standard deviations of the performance of fifth-grade students in the basic Arabic language subject on the test of innovative thinking Pre and post

Group	N	Skill	Pretest		Posttest	
			Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Control	58	Fluency	3.32	1.887	4.42	2.277
		Flexibility	2.21	1.31	3.77	1.627
		Originality	1.81	.703	2.55	1.207
		Total	7.61	2.246	10.74	2.756
Experimental	62	Fluency	3.68	2.170	6.65	3.152
		Flexibility	2.21	1.009	6.12	1.181
		Originality	1.88	.808	4.76	1.208
		Total	7.76	2.955	17.53	4.589

It is noticed from Table (2) that there are apparent differences between the mean of the performance of the 6th grade basic students in the English language subject in the innovative thinking test (fluency, flexibility, and originality) as the experimental group that used creative drama got a mean of (6.65) for the skill of fluency, which is higher than the mean of the control group that studied in the usual way, as it reached (4)

In the skill of flexibility, the experimental group got a mean of (6.12) which is higher than the mean of the control group as it reached (3.77). The experimental group in the skill of originality got a mean of (4.76), which is higher than the mean of the control group that got (2.55). The total number of the innovative thinking test, the experimental group that studied using creative drama got a mean of (17.53) and it is higher than the mean of the control group that was taught by the usual method, as it reached (10.74).

To determine whether the differences between the means are statistically significant at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) the accompanying mono-analysis of variance was applied and the results of the analysis of variance came as follows as in Table (3).

Table 3: One-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) to find the significance of the differences in the performance of the seventh-grade basic students in the English language subject on the innovative thinking test according to the teaching strategy

Source of variance	Skill	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	F value	Sig	ETA square
Pretest	Fluency	249.784	1	249.784	66.315		
	Flexibility	53.515	1	53.515	24.865		
	Originality	14.991	1	14.991	13.913		
	Total	553.358	1	553.358			
Teaching strategy	Fluency	57.011	1	57.011	15.136	0.000	0.196
	Flexibility	105.029	1	105.029	48.801	0.000	0.440
	Originality	75.992	1	75.992	70.527	0.000	0.532
	Total	709.412	1	709.412	119.18	0.000	0.658
ERROR	Fluency	233.529	62	3.767			
	Flexibility	133.434	62	2.152			
	Originality	66.804	62	1.077			
	Total	369.048	62	5.952			
Adjusted total	Fluency	563.785	64				
	Flexibility	276.000	64				
	Originality	161.446	64				
	Total	1669.45	64				

The results in Table (3) indicate that there are statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the performance of the 6th grade students in the English language subject on the innovative thinking test (fluency, flexibility, and originality) in the dimension of the difference in the teaching strategy, according to the variable of the teaching method based on the value of calculated (P), as it reached in the skill of fluency (57.011) and at the level of significance (0.000) and in the skill of flexibility it reached (105.029) and at the level of significance (0.000) and in the skill of originality, it reached (75.992) and at the level of significance (0.000) and it reached in the grand total (709,412), with a significant level (0.000) with this result, the first null hypothesis is rejected, which states:

There are no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the development of innovative thinking among 6th grade students in the English language, due to the use of creative drama, compared to the usual method.

In order to identify the relevance of the differences in the performance of the fifth-grade basic students in the Arabic language subject on the dimensional innovative thinking test (fluency, flexibility, and originality) according to the different teaching strategy, modified arithmetic averages and standard errors were extracted and table (4) shows that.

Table 4: The modified post-arithmetic averages and standard errors of the performance of the seventh-grade basic students in the English language subject on the Innovative Thinking Test (fluency, flexibility, and originality) after the different teaching strategy

Group	Skill	Adjusted mean	Standard error
Control	Fluency	4.600	0.349
	Flexibility	3.659	0.264
	Originality	2.574	0.187
	Total	10.831	0.438
Experimental	Fluency	6.482	0.333
	Flexibility	6.223	0.252
	Originality	4.741	0.178
	Total	17.448	0.418

It is noted from Table (4) that the modified mean performance of the 6th grade basic students in the English language subject on the innovative thinking test (fluency, flexibility, and originality) depending on the different teaching strategy, the experimental group that used creative drama was (6,482) in the skill of fluency which is higher than the mean of the control group which was taught in the usual way, which amounted to (4.600).

In the skill of flexibility, the experimental group got (6.223), which is higher than the control group, whose mean average (3.659), and the mean of the experimental group in the skill of originality was (4.741), which is higher than the mean of the control group as it reached (2.574). As for the grand total, the experimental group got a mean of (17.448), which is higher than the mean of the control group, which amounted to (10.83).

This means that the difference in the performance of the 6th grade students in the English language subject on the post-innovative thinking test (fluency, flexibility, and originality) according to the difference in the teaching strategy was in favor of the experimental group that used the creative drama, when compared with the control group that was taught in the usual way, this difference indicates the existence of an impact of the use of creative drama in innovative thinking among 6th grade students in the English language subject due to the use of creative drama compared to the usual method, as the size of the effect according to the values of ETA square (0.658).

Second: The results related to the second question, which stated:

"What is the effect of using creative drama in teaching English language on the achievement of 6th grade students, compared to the usual method?"

To answer this question and test the hypothesis associated with it, the means and standard deviations of the 6th grade students' performance in the English language subject were calculated on the pre/post thinking test. Table (5) shows that.

Table 5: Means and standard deviations of the performance of 6th grade students in English language on the pre/post-achievement test

Group	N	Pretest	Posttest
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		Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Control	58	16.33	3.45	18.19	4.55
Experimental	62	14.63	2.21	25.24	3.62

It is noticed from Table (5) that there are apparent differences between the means of the 6th grade students' performance in the English language subject on the post-achievement test. The experimental group that was taught using creative drama got a mean of (25.24), which is higher than the mean of the control group that was taught in the usual way as it reached (18.19). To determine whether the differences between the means are statistically significant at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), the accompanying One-Way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) was applied, and the results of the analysis of variance came as shown in Table (6) as follows:

Table 6: One-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) to find the significance of the differences on the performance of the basic seventh grade students in the English language subject on the achievement test according to the teaching strategy

Source of variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	F value	Sig	Eta square
Pretest	151.476	1	151.476	10.418	0.002	
Teaching strategy	850.937	1	850.937	58.524	0.000*	0.486
ERROR	901.481	62	14.540			
Adjusted total	1857.1	64	1857.1			

The results in Table (6) indicate that there are statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), for the performance of 6th grade students in the English language subject on the post-achievement test according to the different teaching strategy, according to the teaching method variable, based on the calculated value of (q) as it reached (58.524) and with the level of significance (0.0000), with this result, the second null hypothesis was rejected, which states: "There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level in the achievement of the 6th grade students in the English language subject attributed to the use of creative drama, compared to the usual way".

In order to know the relevance of the differences in the performance of the 6th grade students in the English language subject on the post-achievement test according to the teaching strategy, the modified means were extracted, and standard errors and Table (7) shows that.

Table 7: The modified post-arithmetic averages and standard errors of the performance of the seventh-grade basic students in the English language subject on the post-achievement test according to the different teaching strategy

Group	Adjusted arithmetic mean	Standard error
Control	18.078	0.686
Experimental	25.341	0.655

It is noticed from Table (7) that the mean of the performance of the 6th grade students in the English language subject on the post-achievement test according to the different teaching strategy of the experimental

group that was taught using the creative drama reached (25.341), which is higher than the mean of the group that was taught in the usual way, which amounted to (18.078).

This means that the difference in the performance of the 6th grade students in the English language subject on the post-achievement test with different teaching strategy was in favor of the experimental group that studied using creative drama when compared with the control group that studied in the usual way, and this difference indicates the existence of an effect of the use of creative drama on the achievement of the 6th grade students in the English language subject due to the use of creative drama compared to the usual method, as the size of the effect according to the ETA values reached (0.486).

Discussion of the Results

First: Discussing the results related to the first question, which stated:

"What is the effect of using creative drama on developing innovative thinking in teaching English among 6th grade students, compared to the usual method?"

The results of the first question as shown in Table (2) showed apparent differences between the arithmetic averages of the performance of sixth-graders on the post test of innovative thinking (fluency, flexibility and originality), as the experimental group that used creative drama got (17.53) which is higher than the control group that Its arithmetic mean (10.74).

The results in Table (3) indicate that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (α 0.05) for the performance of sixth-graders in the English language subject on the Innovative thinking posttest (fluency, flexibility, and originality) according to the difference in the teaching strategy based on the value of calculated (F) Which reached (119.18) and a significant level (0.000), and was in favor of the experimental group.

With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected, which stated that there are no statistically significant differences at (α 0.05 \geq) in the innovative thinking test in the English language subject due to the use of creative drama compared to the usual method.

This result may be attributed to a number of reasons, perhaps the most important of which is that learning using creative drama is a new topic for students, and the new raises interest, increases motivation and excitement, which pushed students to enthusiasm and drive towards learning more than their counterparts who learned in the usual way.

This result may also be explained by the fact that the experimental group students who underwent learning using creative drama were active participants in the educational learning process, as they direct their interests and hobbies in acquiring knowledge through role-playing in their own way under the guidance of the teacher, in this way, their information and skills are acquired more easily and quickly in an atmosphere of vitality, activity, and pleasure, and their ability to generate the largest number of diverse and new ideas, thus, can have a positive impact and create desirable trends in the minds of students who have learned using creative drama more than the control group students who studied Using the normal method.

The creative drama that depends on improvisational acting, role-playing, visualization, and silent gesture, contributes to the development of innovative activities that increase the creative and innovative responses that contribute to expanding the horizon of thinking and self-confidence during the performance of educational tasks, which helps students to acquire educational experiences and employing it in new life situations that increase their motivation for achievement and work away from the monotony and regular teaching methods (Alsurour, 2005).

This result may also be attributed to the fact that creative drama enabled students to use their senses effectively in focus, the accuracy of observation, and imagination, which gained them the ability to install information and transmit it among themselves in a simpler way, increasing the flow of ideas in their imaginations, to find new solutions and alternatives to the topics presented to them and the wording of a number of sentences differs in their meaning, and they are written in their own language.

Bruner's theory of perception emphasizes that creativity is linked to the development of the ability to creative thinking through methods that enable students to confront problems and find appropriate solutions to them, or to use their actions as means of clarification for educational situations, thus encouraging them to self-learning and focus on the information and knowledge taught to them (Bruner, 1985).

The researcher did not find - within the limits of her knowledge - previous studies that combined the effect of using creative drama and the development of innovative thinking, which made this study more important than other studies related to the use of Creative drama.

Second: Discussing the results related to the second question, which stated:

"What is the effect of using creative drama in teaching English on the achievement of sixth-6th graders, compared to the usual method?"

The results of the second question, as indicated in Table (4), showed the existence of apparent differences between the mean of sixth-grade students 'performance on the post-achievement test, as the

experimental group that was taught using creative drama got (25.24), which is higher than the mean for the control group that got (18.19).

The results in Table (5) indicated that there were statistically significant differences at the level of (α 0.05) for the performance of 6th graders in the English language subject on the post-achievement test according to the difference in the teaching strategy based on the calculated value of (F) which amounted to (58,524) and with a significant level (0.000) and in favor of the experimental group. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected, which stated that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the achievement of 6th graders in the English language subject to the use of creative drama compared to the usual method.

The superiority of the creative use of Drama over the usual way may be attributed to the confirmation of students' information through the performance of rhythmic movements, the representation stemming from their feelings, and their understanding of the subject matter and linking it to the reality surrounding them in a practical way.

The result may also be explained by the fact that the creative drama in removing the psychological barriers that separate students from their teacher, and their feeling that they are practicing acting freely, and that they express the educational position in their own way increases their motivation, and draws them towards the proposed idea, deepening their understanding of the topic, and thus improving their performance.

Educational drama is used as an effective method in many educational purposes, due to its ability to refine and show students' abilities, by embodying various dramatic situations that lead to the detection and expression of what he wants by using his movements and senses, and also helps to activate his imagination, which achieves a deep understanding of knowledge and enables him to retrieve the information that he receives very easily.

This result may also be attributed to the students' feeling of pleasure and harmony with their nature, which tends to be spontaneous in expressing what is touring their thought, and thus they learn on their own under the supervision of the teacher who directs them to implement the idea in a way that ensures their understanding of the information in a deeper way and provides them with feedback through raising their imaginations to restore the representative educational position to take root in their minds, as the linguistic structures and meanings contained in the text are no longer static, but rather events that have been performed in a representative manner, and have become entrenched as positions in their imaginations, so that the student is a participant and a spectator increases his listening and focusing on the knowledge and information he receives, and this leads to an improvement in the educational attainment level.

Creative drama contributes to the development of students' communication skills to allow them to develop their personality. When the learner adopts a personality or situation, he becomes formally entrenched in his mind and has the ability to learn and pay attention to all the subtle details and thus be able to absorb the desired educational outcomes and gain the necessary expertise to improve the level of achievement.

The results of the current study are in agreement with the study (Fernsler, 2005), which concluded the effectiveness of using drama in improving students' achievement level.

Recommendations

Based on the result of the first question, "There are statistically significant differences between the average performance of the two study groups on the innovative thinking test (fluency, flexibility, and originality) in the post-test in favor of the experimental group that studied the English language subject using creative drama."

The researcher recommends the following:

- The need to pay attention to the application of creative drama in teaching the English language course because of its positive impact on the development of innovative thinking (fluency, flexibility, and originality) among students.

Based on the result of the second question "There are statistically significant differences between the averages of the performance of the two study groups on the post-achievement test in favor of the experimental group that studied the English language subject using creative drama.

The researcher recommends the following:

Encouraging male and female teachers to use creative drama in teaching the English language because of its impact on improving students' level.

Proposals

Conducting more studies and similar research in teaching the English language course on various learning outcomes, as it is considered a basic subject that includes multiple topics.

Encouraging researchers to conduct research related to the use of creative drama in other subjects such as science and sociology as one of the modern teaching methods.

Holding training courses for English language teachers on the use of creative drama and its use in the educational process, for its ability to develop innovative thinking.

The necessity of working on the use of creative drama by including the English language curriculum and the teacher's guide practical applications related to the information taught to students, so that they form a tributary resource for teachers and students.

References

- Abdulhak Halim Ula. July (2008): The Effects of Creative, Educational Drama Activities on Developing Oral Skills in Primary School Children. *American Journal of Applied Sciences* 5(7): 876-880, www.scipub.org/fulltext/ajas/ajas57876-880.pdf
- Abu Mansour, N. (2018). The Effect of Using Creative Drama in the Development of Innovative Thinking and Achievement in the Teaching of Arabic Language for Fifth Grade Students in the Capital Amman, Unpublished Master thesis, Middle East University, Amman, Jordan. https://meu.edu.jo/library/Theses/5af2b52f00a1a_1.pdf
- Afaneh, Izzo and al-Louh, A. (2008). *Dar Al-Masirah, (Teaching Theater)* (Amman, Jordan, <http://search.shamaa.org/FullRecord?ID=24582>
- Al-Qurashi, A. (2001). *Curricula and Dramatic Introduction*, 1st Edition, Cairo: The World of Books.
- Al-Sorour, N. (2005). *The RUSC Thinking Education Program*. Oman: Debono for printing, publishing and distribution.
- Bati, K.; Ertürk, G. & Kaptan, F. (2009). The awareness levels of pre-school education teachers regarding science process skills, *www.sciencedirect.com, Procedia- Social and Behavioral Sciences, Volume 2, Issue 2, (2010) Pages 1993–1999*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.03.270>
- Bruner, J. S. (1985). "Narrative and paradigmatic modes of thought," in *Learning and Teaching the Ways of Knowing*, ed. E. Eisner (Chicago, IL: The University of Chicago Press).
- Ozdemir, S. M., & Cakmak, A. (2008). The effect of drama education on prospective teachers' creativity. *International Journal of Instruction*, 1, 13-30. http://www.e-iji.net/dosyalar/iji_2008_1_2.pdf
- Petri, H., and Govern, J. (2004). *Motivation: Theory, Research and Applications*, Thomson-Wadsworth, Australia. <https://www.amazon.com/Motivation-Research-Application-Herbert-Petri/dp/1111841098>
- Shaheen, N. (2009). The Impact of Active Learning on Achievement and Development ((*Journal of Scientific Education, Al-Jamaa*)), science processes among fourth-grade students of Egyptian primary school for scientific education, Cairo, Egypt Vol. 12, N. 2.

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